

A Study of Catechol and Pyrogallol Derivatives of Copper

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The complex formation reactions of copper with chelating agents, catechol and pyrogallol, have been carried out by potentiometric and conductometric methods and the correctness of the assumed formation of 1:1 and 1:3 complexes in the system has been further confirmed by preparative studies. The logarithms of formation constants ($\log K_f$) for 1:1 and 1:3 complexes have also been calculated by alternative methods to be 14.27 ± 0.08 ; 13.36 ± 0.09 (catechol system) and 12.36 ± 0.13 ; 11.63 ± 0.13 (pyrogallol system).

Copper, being almost the last member of the first transition series, depicts a strong tendency of complex formation and a considerable amount of literature has accumulated on the subject¹⁻³. Although some studies⁶⁻⁷ have been made on the nature of the complex-forming tendency of copper ions with catechol, no physico-chemical investigation has so far been made on copper-pyrogallol system. In both the systems, no attempt appears to have been made to compute the formation constants from the functions $\bar{n}$ and $\Delta\epsilon$. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make a detailed study on these systems by potentiometric and conductometric techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of E. Merck copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and B.D.H. AnalaR copper nitrate, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were prepared by direct weighing and the strengths checked iodometrically. Solutions of recrystallised catechol and pyrogallol were also prepared by direct weighing. All solutions were made with conductivity water.

pH measurements were carried out at the room temperature with a Cambridge Bench type pH-meter, standardised against 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate solutions. A Philips Magic eye type (P.R. 9500) conductivity bridge was used for conductance measurements.

Lango Flame photometer, model 6, was used for the estimation of potassium. The copper content of the compound was determined iodometrically after decomposing it with nitric acid.

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Alkaline KMnO_4 was found to oxidise catechol quantitatively to CO_2 and water and this method was adopted for the estimation of catechol.

Pyrogallol was also estimated by the oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 method. It was, however, found that pyrogallol was not oxidised completely under these conditions. Hence the pyrogallol content was found empirically by comparing the amount of KMnO_4 consumed by a known weight of the compound and a known weight of pyrogallol under identical conditions.

Potentiometric Studies

As catechol and pyrogallol were found susceptible to oxidation by atmospheric oxygen, all titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere to exclude oxygen from the equilibrium mixture.

The potentiometric titration of copper ions with catechol in presence of 0 and 2 moles of KOH (curves 1 and 2, Fig. 1) indicates chelation which may be represented as:

Addition of catechol to copper nitrate solution lowers the pH of the latter and this lowering is a direct measure of chelation. The nature of these curves is the same, except that the fall in pH in curve 2 (about 4.1 units) is much more as compared to that in curve 1 (about 1.0 unit), indicating a greater tendency for chelation in the alkaline range.

The potentiometric titration of copper nitrate in presence of equimolar concentration of catechol (curve 1, Fig. 2) shows an inflection at $m=2$, indicating formation of a neutral monocatecholate derivative of the type:

As shown later, the neutral monocatecholate may be better assigned the alternative structure, $\frac{1}{2} \text{Cu} [\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$, similar to the one suggested for neutral beryllium monoacetylacetyl⁸. After further addition of alkali, the curve assumes the shape composite of curve 0 and later quarter portion of curve 2, showing disproportionation of 1 : 1 into 1 : 2 complex with the simultaneous precipitation of half of copper as its hydroxide. Thus, in this case inflection occurs at $m=3$, indicating the reaction:

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The correctness of the above reaction has been confirmed by estimating the amount of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, K_2SO_4 , and $\text{K}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$ formed in the reaction:

The titration of copper nitrate with KOH in presence of two moles of catechol (curve 2, Fig. 2) shows inflections at $m=2$ and 4, indicating the reactions:

The precipitated compound dissolves at $m=3.8$ with a rapid rise in pH at $m=4$, indicating the formation of a dicatecholate derivative. Stability of the dicatecholate derivative is further indicated by nonprecipitation of copper hydroxide even after pH of the medium exceeds 11 in presence of higher OH^- ion concentration.

FIG. 1. Potentiometric titrations of copper nitrate (30 ml, 0.05 M) with molar catechol in presence of 0 (curve 1) and 2 (curve 2) ml of molar KOH.

FIG. 2. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent potentiometric titrations of copper nitrate (30 ml, 0.05 M) with molar KOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of molar catechol, respectively.

Similar titrations in presence of 3 moles of catechol (curve 3, Fig. 2) show inflections at $m=2$ and 4, indicating formation of mono- and di-catecholate derivative, respectively. Another inflection at $m=5$, occurring at pH 11.2, corresponds to the neutralisation of excess of catechol present in the system.

FIG. 3

Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent potentiometric titration of copper nitrate (20 ml, 0.05 M) with molar KOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of molar pyrogallol, respectively.

Potentiometric studies of the complex-forming reactions of copper with pyrogallol also indicate the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The equations representing the formation of mono- and di-pyrogallolate derivatives are shown below.

(Curves 1, 2, and 3, Fig. 3)

(Curve 1, Fig. 3)

(Curves 2 and 3, Fig. 3)

(Curve 2, Fig. 3)

The correctness of (b) and (d) reactions has been further confirmed by isolating the amounts of potassium sulphate and the complexes obtained from the reaction mixtures of copper sulphate, pyrogallol, and KOH in different molar ratios.

FIG. 4. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent conductometric titrations of copper nitrate ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$, 20 ml) with KOH (0.10M) in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of catechol (0.10M). Curves 0', 1', 2' and 3' represent above titrations with ammonium hydroxide (0.10M).

FIG. 5. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent conductometric titrations of 20 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ copper nitrate with 0.10M-KOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of pyrogallol (0.10M). Curves 0', 1', 2', and 3' represent above titrations with 0.10M ammonium hydroxide.

Conductometric Studies

The conductometric titrations of copper nitrate with KOH in presence of 0,1,2, and 3 moles of catechol (curves 0,1,2, and 3 of Fig. 4) and 0,1,2, and 3 moles of pyrogallol (curves 0,1,2, and 3 of Fig. 5) show inflections in corroboration with those obtained from potentiometric titrations, although the rapid rise in conductance by the excess of caustic alkali makes these less pronounced.

When KOH was replaced by the weak base, NH_4OH , the above titrations yielded very sharp inflection points (curves 0',1',2', and 3', Fig. 4 and 5), as the excess of NH_4OH did not increase conductance of the medium appreciably.

Preparative Studies

(i) *Reaction of Copper Sulphate (1M) with Catechol (1M) in presence of 3 moles of KOH.*—To a solution of 0.5M copper sulphate (10 ml) containing M catechol (5 ml) was added gradually and with constant stirring M-KOH solution (15 ml). The solution was left for 1 hr.. The precipitated mass was filtered, washed with cold water, and dried. On analysis this was found to be hydrated copper oxide.

To the filtrate was added anhydrous ethanol (ca. 100 ml) for precipitating potassium sulphate. The filtrate was concentrated to about 10 ml and an excess of ethanol was added to precipitate an insoluble product. The product was recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol, dried in an air oven at 100-105°, and analysed. {Found: K, 18.51; Cu, 15.71; catechol, 53.90. $\text{K}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 18.99; Cu, 15.43; catechol, 52.50%}.

(ii). *Reaction of Copper Sulphate (1 M) with Catechol (2 M) in presence of 4M-KOH.*—From the clear solution, obtained by treating 10 ml of 0.5M copper sulphate containing 10 ml of M-catechol with 20 ml of M-KOH, potassium sulphate was precipitated and separated as before. The filtrate was concentrated to about 10 ml. Finally an insoluble product was obtained by addition of an excess of ethanol to the concentrated solution. This was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, dried in air oven at 100-105°, and analysed. {Found: K, 18.48; Cu, 15.33; catechol, 52.16. $\text{K}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 18.99; Cu, 15.43; catechol, 52.50%}.

(iii). *Reaction of Copper Sulphate (1M) with Pyrogallol (1M) in presence of 3 moles of KOH.*—Treatment of copper sulphate (10 ml, 0.5M) in presence of 5 ml of molar pyrogallol with 15 ml of M-KOH provided a clear solution from which the potassium sulphate was precipitated by addition of EtOH (ca. 100 ml). The filtrate was concentrated to about 7 ml by evaporating excess of the solvent. An excess of ethanol was added to the concentrated solution when an insoluble product was obtained. It was recrystallised from EtOH (dil.), dried in air oven at 100°, and analysed. {Found: K, 13.61; Cu, 23.01; pyrogallol, 43.07. $\text{K}[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3)(\text{OH})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 13.98; Cu, 22.72; pyrogallol, 44.36%}.

(iv). *Reaction of Copper Sulphate (1M) with Pyrogallol (2M) in presence of 4 moles of KOH.*—From the clear solution, obtained from copper sulphate, pyrogallol, and KOH

in 1:2:4 ratio, potassium sulphate and the complex were separated as before. The recrystallised copper derivative was analysed. (Found: K, 16.65; Cu, 13.82; pyrogallol, 52.84. $K_2 [Cu(C_6H_4O_3)_2] \cdot 4H_2O$ requires K, 16.93; Cu, 13.76; pyrogallol, 53.75%).

FIG. 6

Curve 1: Potentiometric titration of 50 ml $[2 \times 10^{-2} M$ catechol + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid] with 0.10M-KOH.

Curve 2: Potentiometric titration of 50 ml $[2 \times 10^{-2} M$ catechol + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid + $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ copper nitrate] with 0.10M-KOH.

FIG. 7

Curve 1: Potentiometric titration of 50 ml $[2 \times 10^{-2} M$ pyrogallol + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid] with 0.10M-KOH.

Curve 2: Potentiometric titration of 50 ml $[2 \times 10^{-2} M$ pyrogallol + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid + $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ copper nitrate] with 0.10M-KOH.

Determination of Formation Constants from the Functions $\bar{n}$ and $[A^{2-}]$

Formation constants, K_1 and K_2 , for the systems $(Cu^{2+} + A^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuA$ and $CuA + A^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuA_2^{2-})$ were calculated from the titrations of catechol or pyrogallol and nitric acid in absence and presence of copper ions (curves 1 and 2, Fig. 6; curves 1 and 2, Fig. 7); the ionic strength of the medium was kept approximately constant by using 0.2M potassium nitrate solution. The values of $\bar{n}$ (average number of ligands per metal ion) were plotted against the values of pA (Fig. 8 and 9).

TABLE I

	Log K_1 .	Log K_1' .	Log K_2' .	Log K_2 .
	Copper-catechol system.		Copper-pyrogallol system.	
(i) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values ¹⁰	14.20	13.28	12.49	11.77
(ii) Spreading factor method ⁹	14.20	13.44	..	..
(iii) Correction term method ¹¹	14.22	13.41	12.26	11.96
(iv) Least square treatment ¹¹	14.35	13.27	12.45	11.74

The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by (i) interpolation at half n values, (ii) spreading factor method, (iii) correction term method, and (iv) least square treatment. The final values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are recorded in Table I.

FIG. 8. Degree of formation of $\bar{n}$ as a function of concentration of ligand, A, for copper-oxalate chelate.

FIG. 9. Degree of formation of $\bar{n}$ as a function of ligand concentration, A, for copper-pyrogallate chelate.

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